

ii-Separation Axioms in Topological Spaces

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Abstract. The aim of this paper is to study and investigate the ii-open sets in topological spaces and to obtain a relationship among b-open, pre-open, semi-open, α -open and β -open sets. Some new types of separation axioms such as ii- T_0 , ii- T_1 , ii- T_2 , ii- R_0 and ii- R_1 axioms in topological spaces by using ii-open sets also are introduced. The relationships among ii- T_0 , ii- T_1 , ii- T_2 and some other separation axioms are investigated.

Keywords: ii-open and ii-closed sets; ii-continuous and ii-irresolute functions; ii- T_k ($k = 0, 1, 2$) and ii- R_k ($k = 0, 1$) spaces.

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I. Introduction

In 1963, N. Levine [5] introduced the notion of semi-open sets which is a weaker form of open sets in topological spaces. In 1965, Njastad [11] introduced the notion of α -open sets. In 1975, Maheswari and Prasad [6] used semi-open sets to introduce the concepts of semi- T_0 , semi- T_1 and semi- T_2 spaces. In 1980, Maheswari and Prasad [7] introduced the concept of α - T_2 space. In 1982, Mashhour [8] introduced the notion of pre-open sets and obtained their properties. In 1983, Monsef et al. [1] introduced and investigated the notion of β -open sets in topological spaces. In 1993, Maki et al. [9] introduced the concept of α - T_0 and α - T_0 spaces. In 1996, Andrijevic [2] introduced a new class of generalized open sets, called, b-open sets in topological spaces. This type of open sets were discussed by [4] under the name of γ -open sets. In 2006, Park [12] introduced the concept of b- T_2 spaces. In 2007, Caldas and Jafari [3] introduced and studied b- T_0 and b- T_1 spaces via b-open sets due to Andrijevic [2]. In 2019, Mohammed and Abdullah [10] introduced and investigated the notion of ii-open sets.

II. Preliminaries

Throughout this paper, spaces (X, \mathfrak{T}) , (Y, τ) , and (Z, η) (or simply X , Y and Z) always mean topological spaces on which no separation axioms are assumed unless explicitly stated. Let A be a subset of a space X . For a subset A of X , $\text{Cl}(A)$ and $\text{Int}(A)$ represents the closure of A and Interior of A respectively.

Definition 2.1. A subset A of a topological space (X, \mathfrak{T}) is said to be

- (i) pre-open set [8] if $A \subset \text{Int}(\text{Cl}(A))$;
- (ii) semi-open set [5] if $A \subset \text{Cl}(\text{Int}(A))$;
- (iii) α -open [11] if $A \subset \text{Int}(\text{Cl}(\text{Int}(A)))$;
- (iv) β -open [1] if $A \subset \text{Cl}(\text{Int}(\text{Cl}(A)))$;
- (v) b-open [2] (or γ -open [4]) if $A \subset \text{In}(\text{Cl}(A)) \cup \text{Cl}(\text{Int}(A))$.

The complement of the pre-open (resp. semi-open, α -open, β -open, b-open) set is called pre-closed (resp. semi-closed, α -closed, β -closed, b-closed).

Definition 2.1. A subset A of a topological space (X, \mathfrak{T}) is said to be **ii-open** [10] set if there exists an open set $G \in \mathfrak{T}$, such that

- (i) $G \neq \phi, X$
- (ii) $A \subset \text{Cl}(A \cap G)$
- (iii) $\text{Int}(A) = G$.

The complement of the ii-open set is called ii-closed. We denote the family of all ii-open (resp. ii-closed) sets of a topological space by ii- $O(X)$ (resp. ii- $C(X)$). The ii-closure of a subset A of X , is the intersection of all ii-

closed sets containing A in X and is denoted by $\text{ii-Cl}(A)$. The ii-interior of a subset A of X is the union of all ii-open sets contained in A and is denoted by $\text{ii-Int}(A)$.

Remark 2.2. For a subset of a space, we have following implications:

Where none of the implications is reversible as can be seen from the following examples:

Example 2.3. Let $X = \{a, b, c, d\}$ and $\mathfrak{T} = \{\phi, \{a\}, \{b\}, \{a, b\}, \{a, b, c\}, X\}$. Then

- (1) b-open sets in (X, \mathfrak{T}) are $\phi, X, \{a\}, \{b\}, \{a, b\}, \{a, c\}, \{a, d\}, \{b, c\}, \{b, d\}, \{a, b, c\}, \{a, b, d\}, \{a, c, d\}, \{b, c, d\}$.
- (2) pre-open sets in (X, \mathfrak{T}) are $\phi, X, \{a\}, \{b\}, \{a, b\}, \{a, b, c\}, \{a, b, d\}$.
- (3) semi-open sets in (X, \mathfrak{T}) are $\phi, X, \{a\}, \{b\}, \{a, b\}, \{a, c\}, \{a, d\}, \{b, c\}, \{b, d\}, \{a, b, c\}, \{a, b, d\}, \{a, c, d\}, \{b, c, d\}$.
- (4) α -open sets in (X, \mathfrak{T}) are $\phi, X, \{a\}, \{b\}, \{a, b\}, \{a, b, c\}, \{a, b, d\}$.
- (5) β -open sets in (X, \mathfrak{T}) are $\phi, X, \{a\}, \{b\}, \{a, b\}, \{a, c\}, \{a, d\}, \{b, c\}, \{b, d\}, \{a, b, c\}, \{a, b, d\}, \{a, c, d\}, \{b, c, d\}$.
- (6) ii-open sets in (X, \mathfrak{T}) are $\phi, X, \{a\}, \{b\}, \{a, b\}, \{a, c\}, \{a, d\}, \{b, c\}, \{b, d\}, \{a, b, c\}, \{a, b, d\}, \{a, c, d\}, \{b, c, d\}$.

Example 2.4. Let $X = \{a, b, c\}$ and $\mathfrak{T} = \{\phi, \{a\}, \{b\}, \{a, b\}, X\}$. Then

- (1) b-open sets in (X, \mathfrak{T}) are $\phi, X, \{a\}, \{b\}, \{a, b\}, \{a, c\}, \{b, c\}$.
- (2) pre-open sets in (X, \mathfrak{T}) are $\phi, X, \{a\}, \{b\}, \{a, b\}$.
- (3) semi-open sets in (X, \mathfrak{T}) are $\phi, X, \{a\}, \{b\}, \{a, b\}, \{b, c\}$.
- (4) α -open sets in (X, \mathfrak{T}) are $\phi, X, \{a\}, \{b\}, \{a, b\}$.
- (5) β -open sets in (X, \mathfrak{T}) are $\phi, X, \{a\}, \{b\}, \{a, b\}, \{a, c\}$.
- (6) ii-open sets in (X, \mathfrak{T}) are $\phi, X, \{a\}, \{b\}, \{a, b\}, \{a, c\}, \{b, c\}$.

Example 2.5. Let $X = \{a, b, c\}$ and $\mathfrak{T} = \{\phi, \{a\}, \{b, c\}, X\}$. Then

- (1) b-open sets in (X, \mathfrak{T}) are $\phi, X, \{a\}, \{b\}, \{c\}, \{a, b\}, \{a, c\}, \{b, c\}$.
- (2) pre-open sets in (X, \mathfrak{T}) are $\phi, X, \{a\}, \{b\}, \{c\}, \{a, b\}, \{a, c\}, \{b, c\}$.
- (3) semi-open sets in (X, \mathfrak{T}) are $\phi, X, \{a\}, \{b, c\}$.
- (4) α -open sets in (X, \mathfrak{T}) are $\phi, X, \{a\}, \{b, c\}$.
- (5) β -open sets in (X, \mathfrak{T}) are $\phi, X, \{a\}, \{b\}, \{c\}, \{a, b\}, \{a, c\}, \{b, c\}$.
- (6) ii-open sets in (X, \mathfrak{T}) are $\phi, X, \{a\}, \{b, c\}$.

Example 2.6. Let $X = \{a, b, c, d\}$ and $\mathfrak{T} = \{\phi, \{a\}, \{b, c, d\}, X\}$. Then

(1) b-open sets in (X, \mathfrak{T}) are $\phi, X, \{a\}, \{b\}, \{c\}, \{d\}, \{a, b\}, \{a, c\}, \{a, d\}, \{b, c\}, \{b, d\}, \{c, d\}, \{a, b, c\}, \{a, b, d\}, \{a, c, d\}, \{b, c, d\}$.

(2) pre-open sets in (X, \mathfrak{T}) are $\phi, X, \{a\}, \{b\}, \{c\}, \{d\}, \{a, b\}, \{a, c\}, \{a, d\}, \{b, c\}, \{b, d\}, \{c, d\}, \{a, b, c\}, \{a, b, d\}, \{a, c, d\}, \{b, c, d\}$.

(3) semi-open sets in (X, \mathfrak{T}) are $\phi, X, \{a\}, \{b, c, d\}$.

(4) α -open sets in (X, \mathfrak{T}) are $\phi, X, \{a\}, \{b, c, d\}$.

(5) β -open sets in (X, \mathfrak{T}) are $\phi, X, \{a\}, \{b\}, \{c\}, \{d\}, \{a, b\}, \{a, c\}, \{a, d\}, \{b, c\}, \{b, d\}, \{c, d\}, \{a, b, c\}, \{a, b, d\}, \{a, c, d\}, \{b, c, d\}$.

(6) ii-open sets in (X, \mathfrak{T}) are $\phi, X, \{a\}, \{b\}, \{c\}, \{d\}, \{b, c\}, \{b, d\}, \{c, d\}, \{b, c, d\}$.

Remark 2.7. The concepts of ii-open and pre-open sets are independent as shown in the above examples.

Remark 2.8. The concepts of ii-open and β -open sets are independent as shown in the above examples.

Definition 2.9. A space X is said to be:

(i) **b-T₀** [3] if for each pair of distinct points x and y in X , there exists a b-open set G containing x but not y or a b-open set H containing y but not x .

(ii) **b-T₁** [3] if for each pair of distinct points x, y in X , there exist a b-open set G containing x but not y and a b-open set H containing y but not x .

(iii) **b-T₂** [12] if for each pair of distinct points x, y of X , there exist two disjoint b-open sets U and V containing x and y respectively.

Definition 2.10. A space X is said to be:

(i) **α -T₀** [9] if for each pair of distinct points x and y in X , there exists an α -open set G containing x but not y or an α -open set H containing y but not x .

(ii) **α -T₁** [9] if for each pair of distinct points x, y in X , there exist an α -open set G containing x but not y and an α -open set H containing y but not x .

(iii) **α -T₂** [7] if for each pair of distinct points x, y of X , there exist two disjoint α -open sets U and V containing x and y respectively.

Definition 2.11. A space X is said to be:

(i) **semi-T₀** [6] if for each pair of distinct points x and y in X , there exists a semi-open set G containing x but not y or a semi-open set H containing y but not x .

(ii) **semi-T₁** [6] if for each pair of distinct points x, y in X , there exist a semi-open set G containing x but not y and a semi-open set H containing y but not x .

(iii) **semi-T₂** [6] if for each pair of distinct points x, y of X , there exist two disjoint semi-open sets U and V containing x and y respectively.

Theorem 2.12. (i) Every open set is ii-open.

(ii) Every α -open set is ii-open.

(iii) Every semi-open set is ii-open.

(iv) Every ii-open set is b-open.

Definition 2.13. Let X and Y be topological spaces. A function $f : X \rightarrow Y$ is said to be **ii-continuous** if the inverse image of every open set in Y is ii-open in X .

Definition 2.14. Let X and Y be topological spaces. A function $f : X \rightarrow Y$ is said to be **ii-closed** if the image of every closed set in X is ii-closed in Y .

Definition 2.15. Let X and Y be topological spaces. A function $f : X \rightarrow Y$ is said to be **ii-irresolute** if the inverse image of every ii-closed set in Y is ii-closed in X .

Definition 2.16. Let X be a topological space. A subset $N \subset X$ is called an **ii-neighbourhood** (briefly **ii-nhd**) of a point $x \in X$ if there exists an ii-open set G such that $x \in G \subset N$.

III. ii- T_0 Spaces

In this section, we define ii- T_0 space and study some of their properties via some other weaker forms of open sets.

Definition 3.1. A topological space (X, \mathfrak{T}) is said to be **ii- T_0** if for each pair of distinct points x, y in X , there exists an ii-open set U such that either $x \in U$ and $y \notin U$ or $x \notin U$ and $y \in U$.

Theorem 3.2. (i) Every semi- T_0 space is ii- T_0 .

(ii) Every α - T_0 space is ii- T_0 .

(iii) Every ii- T_0 space is b- T_0 .

Proof. (i) Let X be a semi- T_0 space. Let x and y be any two distinct points in X . Since X is semi- T_0 , there exists a semi-open set U such that $x \in U$ and $y \notin U$ or $y \in U$ and $x \notin U$. By **Theorem 2.12 (iii)**, U is an ii-open set such that $x \in U$ and $y \notin U$ or $y \in U$ and $x \notin U$. Thus X is ii- T_0 .

(ii) Since every α -open set is ii-open and so, by the **Theorem 2.12 (ii)**, every α - T_0 space is ii- T_0 .

(iii) Since every ii-open set is b-open and so, by the **Theorem 2.12 (iv)**, every ii- T_0 space is b- T_0 .

Theorem 3.3. Every topological space is ii- T_0 .

Proof. Since every open set is ii-open and so, by the **Theorem 2.12 (i)**, every T_0 space is ii- T_0 .

Theorem 3.4. A topological space (X, \mathfrak{T}) is ii- T_0 if and only if for each pair of distinct points x, y of X , $\text{ii-Cl}(\{x\}) \neq \text{ii-Cl}(\{y\})$.

Proof. Necessity. Let (X, \mathfrak{T}) be an ii- T_0 space and x, y be any two distinct points of X . There exists an ii-open set U containing x or y , say x but not y . Then $X - U$ is an ii-closed set which does not contain x but contains y . Since $\text{ii-bCl}(\{y\})$ is the smallest ii-closed set containing y , $\text{ii-Cl}(\{y\}) \subset X - U$ and therefore $x \notin \text{ii-Cl}(\{y\})$. Consequently $\text{ii-Cl}(\{x\}) \neq \text{ii-Cl}(\{y\})$.

Sufficiency. Suppose that $x, y \in X$, $x \neq y$ and $\text{ii-Cl}(\{x\}) \neq \text{ii-Cl}(\{y\})$. Let z be a point of X such that $z \in \text{ii-Cl}(\{x\})$ but $z \notin \text{ii-Cl}(\{y\})$. We claim that $x \notin \text{ii-Cl}(\{y\})$. For, if $x \in \text{ii-Cl}(\{y\})$ then $\text{ii-Cl}(\{x\}) \subset \text{ii-Cl}(\{y\})$. This contradicts the fact that $z \notin \text{ii-Cl}(\{y\})$. Consequently x belongs to the ii-open set $X - \text{ii-Cl}(\{y\})$ to which y does not belong.

Theorem 3.5. Every subspace of an ii- T_0 space is ii- T_0 .

Proof. Let (Y, τ) be a subspace of a topological space (X, \mathfrak{T}) , where τ is the relative topology of \mathfrak{T} on Y . Let x, y be two distinct points of Y . As $Y \subset X$, x and y are also distinct points of X and there exists an ii-open set G such that $x \in G$ but $y \notin G$, since X is ii- T_0 . Then $G \cap Y$ is an ii-open set in (Y, τ) which contains x but does not contain y . Hence (Y, τ) is an ii- T_0 space.

IV. ii- T_1 Spaces

In this section, we define ii- T_1 space and study some of their properties via some other weaker forms of open sets.

Definition 4.1. A topological space (X, \mathfrak{T}) is said to be **ii- T_1** if for each pair of distinct points x, y in X , there exist two ii-open sets U and V such that $x \in U$ but $y \notin U$ and $y \in V$ but $x \notin V$.

Theorem 4.2. (i) Every semi- T_1 space is ii- T_1 .

(ii) Every α - T_1 space is ii- T_1 .

(iii) Every ii- T_1 space is b- T_1 .

Proof. (i). Suppose X is a semi- T_1 space. Let x and y be two distinct points in X . Since X is semi- T_1 , there exist semi-open sets U and V such that $x \in U$ but $y \notin U$ and $y \in V$ but $x \notin V$. By **Theorem 2.12 (iii)**, every semi-open set is ii-open, so U and V are ii-open sets such that $x \in U$ but $y \notin U$ and $y \in V$ but $x \notin V$. Hence X is ii- T_1 .

(ii). Since every α -open set is ii-open and so, by the **Theorem 2.12 (ii)**, every α - T_1 space is ii- T_1 .

(iii) Since every ii-open set is b-open and so, by the **Theorem 2.12 (iv)**, every ii- T_1 space is b- T_1 .

Theorem 4.3. Let $f : X \rightarrow Y$ be an ii-irresolute, injective map. If Y is ii- T_1 , then X is ii- T_1 .

Proof. Assume that Y is ii- T_1 . Let $x, y \in Y$ with $x \neq y$. Then there exists a pair of ii-open sets U, V of Y such that $f(x) \in U, f(y) \in V$ and $f(x) \notin V, f(y) \notin U$. Then $x \in f^{-1}(U), y \notin f^{-1}(U)$ and $y \in f^{-1}(V), x \notin f^{-1}(V)$. Since f is ii-irresolute, X is ii- T_1 .

Theorem 4.4. A topological space (X, \mathfrak{T}) is ii- T_1 if and only if the singletons are ii-closed sets.

Proof. Let (X, \mathfrak{T}) be ii- T_1 and x be any point of X . Suppose $y \in X - \{x\}$, then $x \neq y$ and so there exists an ii-open set U such that $y \in U$ but $x \notin U$. Consequently $y \in U \subset X - \{x\}$, that is $X - \{x\} = \cup \{U : y \in X - \{x\}\}$ which is ii-open.

Conversely, suppose $\{p\}$ is ii-closed for every $p \in X$. Let $x, y \in X$ with $x \neq y$. Now $x \neq y$ implies $y \in X - \{x\}$. Hence $X - \{x\}$ is an ii-open set contains y but not x . Similarly $X - \{y\}$ is an ii-open set contains x but not y . Accordingly, X is an ii- T_1 space.

Theorem 4.5. Let $f : X \rightarrow Y$ be bijective.

(i) If f is ii-continuous and (Y, \mathfrak{T}_2) is T_1 , then (X, \mathfrak{T}_1) is ii- T_1 .

(ii) If f is ii-open and (X, \mathfrak{T}_1) is ii- T_1 , then (Y, \mathfrak{T}_2) is ii- T_1 .

Proof. Let $f : (X, \mathfrak{T}_1) \rightarrow (Y, \mathfrak{T}_2)$ be bijective.

(i) Suppose $f : (X, \mathfrak{T}_1) \rightarrow (Y, \mathfrak{T}_2)$ is ii-continuous and (Y, \mathfrak{T}_2) is T_1 . Let $x_1, x_2 \in X$ with $x_1 \neq x_2$. Since f is bijective, $y_1 = f(x_1) \neq f(x_2) = y_2$ for some $y_1, y_2 \in Y$. Since (Y, \mathfrak{T}_2) is T_1 , there exist open sets G and H such that $y_1 \in G$ but $y_2 \notin G$ and $y_2 \in H$ but $y_1 \notin H$. Since f is bijective, $x_1 = f^{-1}(y_1) \in f^{-1}(G)$ but $x_2 = f^{-1}(y_2) \notin f^{-1}(G)$ and $x_2 = f^{-1}(y_2) \in f^{-1}(H)$ but $x_1 = f^{-1}(y_1) \notin f^{-1}(H)$. Since f is ii-continuous, $f^{-1}(G)$ and $f^{-1}(H)$ are ii-open sets in (X, \mathfrak{T}_1) . It follows that (X, \mathfrak{T}_1) is ii- T_1 . This proves (i).

(ii) Suppose f is ii-open and (X, \mathfrak{T}_1) is ii- T_1 . Let $y_1 \neq y_2 \in Y$. Since f is bijective, there exist x_1, x_2 in X , such that $y_1 = f(x_1)$ and $f(x_2) = y_2$ with $x_1 \neq x_2$. Since (X, \mathfrak{T}_1) is ii- T_1 , there exist ii-open sets G and H in X such that $x_1 \in G$ but $x_2 \notin G$ and $x_2 \in H$ but $x_1 \notin H$. Since f is ii-open, $f(G)$ and $f(H)$ are ii-open in Y such that $y_1 = f(x_1) \in f(G)$ and $y_2 = f(x_2) \in f(H)$. Again since f is bijective, $y_2 = f(x_2) \notin f(G)$ and $y_1 = f(x_1) \notin f(H)$. Thus (Y, \mathfrak{T}_2) is ii- T_1 . This proves (ii).

Definition 4.6. A topological space (X, \mathfrak{T}) is said to be **ii-symmetric** if for x and y in X , $x \in \text{ii-Cl}(\{y\})$ implies $y \in \text{ii-Cl}(\{x\})$.

Theorem 4.7. If (X, \mathfrak{T}) is a topological space, then the following are equivalent:

(i) (X, \mathfrak{T}) is an ii-symmetric space.

(ii) $\{x\}$ is ii-closed, for each $x \in X$.

Proof. (i) \Rightarrow (ii). Assume that $\{x\} \subset U \in \text{ii-O}(X)$, but $\text{ii-Cl}(\{x\}) \not\subset U$. Then $\text{ii-Cl}(\{x\}) \cap (X - U) \neq \emptyset$. Now, we take $y \in \text{ii-Cl}(\{x\}) \cap (X - U)$, then by hypothesis $x \in \text{ii-Cl}(\{y\}) \subset X - U$ and $x \notin U$, which is a contradiction. Therefore $\{x\}$ is ii-closed, for each $x \in X$.

(ii) \Rightarrow (i). Assume that $x \in \text{ii-Cl}(\{y\})$, but $y \notin \text{ii-Cl}(\{x\})$. Then $\{y\} \subset X - \text{ii-Cl}(\{x\})$ and hence $\text{ii-Cl}(\{y\}) \subset X - \text{ii-Cl}(\{x\})$. Therefore $x \in X - \text{ii-Cl}(\{x\})$, which is a contradiction and hence $y \in \text{ii-Cl}(\{x\})$.

Corollary 4.8. If a topological space (X, \mathfrak{T}) is an ii- T_1 space, then it is ii-symmetric.

Proof. In an $ii-T_1$ space, every singleton is ii -closed (**Theorem 4.4**) and therefore is by **Theorem 4.7**, (X, \mathfrak{T}) is ii -symmetric.

Corollary 4.9. If a topological space (X, \mathfrak{T}) is ii -symmetric and $ii-T_0$, then (X, \mathfrak{T}) is $ii-T_1$.

Proof. Let $x \neq y$ and as (X, \mathfrak{T}) is $ii-T_0$, we may assume that $x \in U \subset X - \{y\}$ for some $U \in ii-O(X)$. Then $x \notin ii-Cl(\{y\})$ and hence $y \notin ii-Cl(\{x\})$. There exists an ii -open set V such that $y \in V \subset X - \{x\}$ and thus (X, \mathfrak{T}) is an $ii-T_1$ space.

V. $ii-T_2$ Spaces

In this section, we introduce $ii-T_2$ space and investigate some of their basic properties via some other weaker forms of open sets.

Definition 5.1. A space X is said to be $ii-T_2$ if for every pair of distinct points x and y in X , there exist disjoint ii -open sets U and V of X containing x and y respectively.

Remark 5.2. For a space, we have following implications:

Where none of the implications are reversible as can be seen from the following examples.

Example 5.3. Consider the space (X, \mathfrak{T}) , where $X = \{a, b, c, d\}$ and $\mathfrak{T} = \{\phi, \{a\}, \{b\}, \{a, b\}, \{a, b, c\}, X\}$. Clearly (X, \mathfrak{T}) is $ii-T_1$ as well as $b-T_1$. But it is neither T_1 nor $\alpha-T_1$.

Example 5.4. Consider the space (X, \mathfrak{T}) , where $X = \{a, b, c, d\}$ and $\mathfrak{T} = \{\phi, \{a, b\}, \{a, b, c\}, \{a, b, d\}, X\}$. Then (X, \mathfrak{T}) is $b-T_1$ but not $ii-T_1$. But it is neither $semi-T_1$ nor $\alpha-T_1$.

Example 5.5. Consider the space (X, \mathfrak{T}) , where $X = \{a, b, c\}$ and $\mathfrak{T} = \{\phi, \{a, b\}, X\}$. Then (X, \mathfrak{T}) is $b-T_2$ but not $ii-T_2$. But it is neither $semi-T_2$ nor $\alpha-T_2$.

Example 5.6. Consider the space (X, \mathfrak{T}) , where $X = \{a, b, c\}$ and $\mathfrak{T} = \{\phi, \{a\}, \{b, c\}, X\}$. Then (X, \mathfrak{T}) is $b-T_2$ but not $ii-T_2$. But it is neither $semi-T_2$ nor $\alpha-T_2$.

Example 5.7. Consider the space (X, \mathfrak{T}) , where $X = \{a, b, c, d\}$ and $\mathfrak{T} = \{\phi, \{a\}, \{b\}, \{a, b\}, X\}$. Then (X, \mathfrak{T}) is $semi-T_2$ as well as $ii-T_2$. But it is not $\alpha-T_2$.

Example 5.8. Consider the space (X, \mathfrak{T}) , where $X = \{a, b, c\}$ and $\mathfrak{T} = \{\phi, \{a\}, \{b, c\}, X\}$. Then (X, \mathfrak{T}) is $b-T_0$. But it is neither $ii-T_0$ nor $\alpha-T_0$.

Theorem 5.9. (i) Every $semi-T_2$ space is $ii-T_2$.

(ii) Every $\alpha-T_2$ space is $ii-T_2$.

(iii) Every $ii-T_2$ space is $b-T_2$.

Proof. (i) Let X be a semi- T_2 space. Let x and y be two distinct points in X . Since X is semi- T_2 , there exist disjoint semi-open sets U and V such that $x \in U$ and $y \in V$. By **Theorem 2.12 (iii)**, U and V are disjoint ii-open sets such that $x \in U$ and $y \in V$. Hence X is ii- T_2 .

(ii) Suppose X is α - T_2 space. Let x and y be two distinct points in X . Since X is α - T_2 , there exist disjoint α -open sets U and V such that $x \in U$ and $y \in V$. By **Theorem 2.12 (ii)**, U and V are disjoint ii-open sets such that $x \in U$ and $y \in V$. Hence X is ii- T_2 .

(iii) Suppose X is ii- T_2 space. Let x and y be two distinct points in X . Since X is ii- T_2 , there exist disjoint ii-open sets U and V such that $x \in U$ and $y \in V$. By **Theorem 2.12 (iv)**, U and V are disjoint b-open sets such that $x \in U$ and $y \in V$. Hence X is b- T_2 .

Theorem 5.10. Every ii- T_2 space is ii- T_1 .

Proof. Let X be an ii- T_2 space. Let x and y be two distinct points of X . Since X is ii- T_2 , there exist disjoint ii-open sets U and V such that $x \in U$ and $y \in V$. Since U and V are disjoint, so $x \in U$ but $y \notin U$ and $y \in V$ but $x \notin V$. Hence X is ii- T_1 .

Theorem 5.11. For a topological space X , the following are equivalent:

(i) X is an ii- T_2 space.

(ii) Let $x \in X$. Then for each $x \neq y$, there exists an ii-open set U such that $x \in U$ and $y \notin \text{ii-Cl}(U)$.

(iii) For each $x \in X$, $\bigcap \{\text{ii-Cl}(U) : U \in \text{ii-O}(X) \text{ and } x \in U\} = \{x\}$.

Proof. (i) \Rightarrow (ii). Suppose X is an ii- T_2 space. Then for each $x \neq y$, there exist disjoint ii-open sets U and V such that $x \in U$ and $y \in V$. Since V is ii-open, V^c is ii-closed and $U \subset V^c$. This implies that $\text{ii-Cl}(U) \subset V^c$. Since $y \notin V^c$, $y \notin \text{ii-Cl}(U)$.

(ii) \Rightarrow (iii). If $y \neq x$, then there exists an ii-open set U such that $x \in U$ and $y \notin \text{ii-Cl}(U)$. Therefore $y \notin \bigcap \{\text{ii-Cl}(U) : U \in \text{ii-O}(X) \text{ and } x \in U\}$. Therefore $\bigcap \{\text{ii-Cl}(U) : U \in \text{ii-O}(X) \text{ and } x \in U\} = \{x\}$. This proves (iii).

(iii) \Rightarrow (i). Let $y \neq x$ in X . Then $y \notin \{x\} = \bigcap \{\text{ii-Cl}(U) : U \in \text{ii-O}(X) \text{ and } x \in U\}$. This implies that there exists an ii-open set U such that $x \in U$ and $y \notin \text{ii-Cl}(U)$. Let $V = (\text{ii-Cl}(U))^c$. Then V is ii-open and $y \in V$. Now $U \cap V = U \cap (\text{ii-Cl}(U))^c \subset U \cap (U)^c = \phi$. Therefore, X is ii- T_2 space.

Theorem 5.12. Let $f : X \rightarrow Y$ be a bijection.

(i) If f is ii-open and X is T_2 , then Y is ii- T_2 .

(ii) If f is ii-continuous and Y is T_2 , then X is ii- T_2 .

Proof. Let $f : X \rightarrow Y$ be a bijection.

(i) Suppose f is ii-open and X is T_2 . Let $y_1 \neq y_2 \in Y$. Since f is a bijection. There exist x_1, x_2 in X such that $f(x_1) = y_1$ and $f(x_2) = y_2$ with $x_1 \neq x_2$. Since X is T_2 , there exist disjoint open sets U and V in X such that $x_1 \in U$ and $x_2 \in V$. Since f is ii-open, $f(U)$ and $f(V)$ are ii-open in Y such that $y_1 = f(x_1) \in f(U)$ and $y_2 = f(x_2) \in f(V)$. Again since f is a bijection, $f(U)$ and $f(V)$ are disjoint in Y . Thus Y is ii- T_2 .

(ii) Suppose $f : X \rightarrow Y$ is ii-continuous and Y is T_2 . Let $x_1, x_2 \in X$ with $x_1 \neq x_2$. Let $y_1 = f(x_1)$ and $y_2 = f(x_2)$. Since f is one-one, $y_1 \neq y_2$. Since Y is T_2 , there exist disjoint open sets U and V containing y_1 and y_2 respectively. Since f is ii-continuous bijective, $f^{-1}(U)$ and $f^{-1}(V)$ are disjoint ii-open sets containing x_1 and x_2 respectively. Thus X is ii- T_2 .

Theorem 5.13. A topological space (X, \mathfrak{T}) is ii- T_2 if and only if the intersection of all ii-closed, ii-neighbourhoods of each point of the space is reduced to that point.

Proof. Let (X, \mathfrak{T}) be ii- T_2 and $x \in X$. Then for each $y \neq x$ in X , there exist disjoint ii-open sets U and V such that $x \in U$, $y \in V$. Now $U \cap V = \phi$ implies $x \in U \subset V^c$. Therefore V^c is an ii-neighbourhood of x . Since V is ii-open, V^c is ii-closed and ii-neighbourhood of x to which y does not belong. That is there is an ii-closed, ii-

neighbourhoods of x which does not contain y . So we get the intersection of all ii-closed, ii-neighbourhood of x is $\{x\}$.

Conversely, let $x, y \in X$ such that $x \neq y$ in X . Then by assumption, there exist an ii-closed, ii-neighbourhood V of x such that $y \notin V$. Now there exists an ii-open set U such that $x \in U \subset V$. Thus U and V^c are disjoint ii-open sets containing x and y respectively. Thus (X, \mathfrak{T}) is ii- T_2 .

Theorem 5.14. If $f : X \rightarrow Y$ be bijective, ii-irresolute map and X is ii- T_2 , then (X, \mathfrak{T}_2) is ii- T_2 .

Proof. Suppose $f : (X, \mathfrak{T}_1) \rightarrow (Y, \mathfrak{T}_2)$ is bijective. f is ii-irresolute, and (Y, \mathfrak{T}_2) is ii- T_2 . Let $x_1, x_2 \in X$ with $x_1 \neq x_2$. Since f is bijective, $y_1 = f(x_1) \neq f(x_2) = y_2$ for some $y_1, y_2 \in Y$. Since (Y, \mathfrak{T}_2) is ii- T_2 , there exist disjoint ii-open sets G and H such that $y_1 \in G$ and $y_2 \in H$. Again since f is bijective, $x_1 = f^{-1}(y_1) \in f^{-1}(G)$ and $x_2 = f^{-1}(y_2) \in f^{-1}(H)$. Since f is ii-irresolute, $f^{-1}(G)$ and $f^{-1}(H)$ are ii-open sets in (X, \mathfrak{T}_1) . Also f is bijective, $G \cap H = \phi$ implies that $f^{-1}(G) \cap f^{-1}(H) = f^{-1}(G \cap H) = f^{-1}(\phi) = \phi$. It follows that (X, \mathfrak{T}_2) is ii- T_2 .

VI. ii- R_k Space ($k = 0, 1$)

In this section, new classes of topological spaces called, ii- R_0 and ii- R_1 spaces are introduced.

Definition 6.1. A topological space (X, \mathfrak{T}) is said to be **ii- R_0** if U is an ii-open set and $x \in U$ then $\text{ii-Cl}(\{x\}) \subset U$.

Theorem 6.2. For a topological space (X, \mathfrak{T}) the following properties are equivalent:

- (i) (X, \mathfrak{T}) is ii- R_0 .
- (ii) For any $F \in \text{ii-C}(X)$, $x \notin F$ implies $F \subset U$ and $x \notin U$ for some $U \in \text{ii-O}(X)$.
- (iii) For any $F \in \text{ii-C}(X)$, $x \notin F$ implies $F \cap \text{ii-Cl}(\{x\}) = \phi$.
- (iv) For any distinct points x and y of X , either $\text{ii-Cl}(\{x\}) = \text{ii-Cl}(\{y\})$ or $\text{ii-Cl}(\{x\}) \cap \text{ii-Cl}(\{y\}) = \phi$.

Proof. (i) \Rightarrow (ii). Let $F \in \text{ii-C}(X)$ and $x \notin F$. Then by (i), $\text{ii-Cl}(\{x\}) \subset X - F$. Set $U = X - \text{ii-Cl}(\{x\})$, then U is an ii-open set such that $F \subset U$ and $x \notin U$.

(ii) \Rightarrow (iii). Let $F \in \text{ii-C}(X)$ and $x \notin F$. There exists $U \in \text{ii-O}(X)$ such that $F \subset U$ and $x \notin U$. Since $U \in \text{ii-O}(X)$, $U \cap \text{ii-Cl}(\{x\}) = \phi$ and $F \cap \text{ii-Cl}(\{x\}) = \phi$.

(iii) \Rightarrow (iv). Suppose that $\text{ii-Cl}(\{x\}) \neq \text{ii-Cl}(\{y\})$ for distinct points $x, y \in X$. There exists $z \in \text{ii-Cl}(\{x\})$ such that $z \notin \text{ii-Cl}(\{y\})$ (or $z \in \text{ii-Cl}(\{y\})$ such that $z \notin \text{ii-Cl}(\{x\})$). There exists $V \in \text{ii-O}(X)$ such that $y \notin V$ and $z \in V$; hence $x \in V$. Therefore, we have $x \notin \text{ii-Cl}(\{y\})$. By (iii), we obtain $\text{ii-Cl}(\{x\}) \cap \text{ii-Cl}(\{y\}) = \phi$.

(iv) \Rightarrow (i). Let $V \in \text{ii-O}(X)$ and $x \in V$. For each $y \notin V$, $x \neq y$ and $x \notin \text{ii-Cl}(\{y\})$. This shows that $\text{ii-Cl}(\{x\}) \neq \text{ii-Cl}(\{y\})$. By (iv), $\text{ii-Cl}(\{x\}) \cap \text{ii-Cl}(\{y\}) = \phi$ for each $y \in X - V$ and hence $\text{ii-Cl}(\{x\}) \cap (\cup_{y \in X - V} \text{ii-Cl}(\{y\})) = \phi$. On other hand, since $V \in \text{ii-O}(X)$ and $y \in X - V$, we have $\text{ii-Cl}(\{y\}) \subset X - V$ and hence $X - V = \cup_{y \in X - V} \text{ii-Cl}(\{y\})$. Therefore, we obtain $(X - V) \cap \text{ii-Cl}(\{x\}) = \phi$ and $\text{ii-Cl}(\{x\}) \subset V$. This shows that (X, \mathfrak{T}) is an ii- R_0 space.

Theorem 6.3. If a topological space (X, \mathfrak{T}) is ii- T_0 and an ii- R_0 space then it is ii- T_1 .

Proof. Let x and y be any distinct points of X . Since X is ii- T_0 , there exists an ii-open set U such that $x \in U$ and $y \notin U$. As $x \in U$ implies that $\text{ii-Cl}(\{x\}) \subset U$. Since $y \notin U$, so $y \notin \text{ii-Cl}(\{x\})$. Hence $y \in V = X - \text{ii-Cl}(\{x\})$ and it is clear that $x \notin V$. Hence it follows that there exist ii-open sets U and V containing x and y respectively, such that $y \notin U$ and $x \notin V$. This implies that X is ii- T_1 .

Theorem 6.4. For a topological space (X, \mathfrak{T}) the following properties are equivalent:

- (i) (X, \mathfrak{T}) is ii- R_0 .
- (ii) $x \in \text{ii-Cl}(\{y\})$ if and only if $y \in \text{ii-Cl}(\{x\})$, for any points x and y in X .

Proof. (i) \Rightarrow (ii). Assume that X is $ii-R_0$. Let $x \in ii-Cl(\{y\})$ and V be any ii -open set such that $y \in V$. Now, by hypothesis, $x \in V$. Therefore, every ii -open set which contain y contains x also. Hence $y \in ii-Cl(\{x\})$.

(ii) \Rightarrow (i). Let U be an ii -open set and $x \in U$. If $y \notin U$, then $x \notin ii-Cl(\{y\})$ and hence $y \notin ii-Cl(\{x\})$. This implies that $ii-Cl(\{x\}) \subset U$. Hence (X, \mathfrak{T}) is $ii-R_0$.

From **Definition 4.6** and **Theorem 6.4**, the notions of ii -symmetric and $ii-R_0$ are equivalent.

Definition 6.5. Let A be a subset of a topological space (X, \mathfrak{T}) . The **ii-kernel** of A , denoted by $ii-ker(A)$ is defined to be the set

$$ii-ker(A) = \bigcap \{U \in ii-O(X) : A \subset U\}.$$

Theorem 6.6. Let (X, \mathfrak{T}) be a topological space and $x \in X$. Then $y \in ii-ker(\{x\})$ if and only if $x \in ii-Cl(\{y\})$.

Proof. Suppose that $y \notin ii-ker(\{x\})$. Then there exists an ii -open set V containing x such that $y \notin V$. Therefore, we have $x \notin ii-Cl(\{y\})$. The proof of the converse case can be done similarly.

Theorem 6.7. Let (X, \mathfrak{T}) be a topological space and A be a subset of X . Then, $ii-ker(A) = \{x \in X : ii-Cl(\{x\}) \cap A \neq \emptyset\}$.

Proof. Let $x \in ii-ker(A)$ and suppose $ii-Cl(\{x\}) \cap A = \emptyset$. Hence $x \notin X - ii-Cl(\{x\})$ which is an ii -open set containing A . This is impossible, since $x \in ii-ker(A)$. Consequently, $ii-Cl(\{x\}) \cap A \neq \emptyset$. Next, let $x \in X$ such that $ii-Cl(\{x\}) \cap A \neq \emptyset$ and suppose that $x \notin ii-ker(A)$. Then, there exists an ii -open set V containing A and $x \notin V$. Let $y \in ii-Cl(\{x\}) \cap A$. Hence, V is an ii -neighbourhood of y which does not contain x . By this contradiction $x \in ii-ker(A)$ and the claim.

Definition 6.8. A subset A of a topological space X is called an **ii-difference set** (briefly, **ii-D-set**) if there are $U, V \in ii-O(X)$ such that $U \neq X$ and $A = U - V$.

Theorem 6.9. The following properties hold for the subsets A, B of a topological space (X, \mathfrak{T}) :

- (i) $A \subset ii-ker(A)$.
- (ii) $A \subset B$ implies that $ii-ker(A) \subset ii-ker(B)$.
- (iii) If A is ii -open in (X, \mathfrak{T}) , then $A = ii-ker(A)$.
- (iv) $ii-ker(ii-ker(A)) = ii-ker(A)$.

Proof. (i), (ii) and (iii) are immediate consequences of **Definition 6.5**. To prove (iv), first observe that by (i) and (ii), we have $ii-ker(A) \subset ii-ker(ii-ker(A))$. If $x \notin ii-ker(A)$, then there exists $U \in ii-O(X)$ such that $A \subset U$ and $x \notin U$. Hence $ii-ker(A) \subset U$, and so we have $x \notin ii-ker(ii-ker(A))$. Thus $ii-ker(ii-ker(A)) = ii-ker(A)$.

Proposition 6.10. If a singleton $\{x\}$ is an ii -D-set of (X, \mathfrak{T}) , then $ii-ker(\{x\}) \neq X$.

Proof. Since $\{x\}$ is an ii -D-set of (X, \mathfrak{T}) , then there exist two subsets $U_1, U_2 \in ii-O(X)$ such that $\{x\} = U_1 - U_2$, $\{x\} \subset U_1$ and $U_1 \neq X$. Thus, we have that $ii-ker(\{x\}) \subset U_1 \neq X$ and so $ii-ker(\{x\}) \neq X$.

Theorem 6.11. The following statements are equivalent for any points x and y in a topological space (X, \mathfrak{T}) :

- (i) $ii-ker(\{x\}) \neq ii-ker(\{y\})$.
- (ii) $ii-Cl(\{x\}) \neq ii-Cl(\{y\})$.

Proof. (i) \Rightarrow (ii). Suppose that $ii-ker(\{x\}) \neq ii-ker(\{y\})$, then there exists a point z in X such that $z \in ii-ker(\{x\})$ and $z \notin ii-ker(\{y\})$. From $z \in ii-ker(\{x\})$ it follows that $\{x\} \cap ii-Cl(\{z\}) \neq \emptyset$ which implies $x \in ii-Cl(\{z\})$. By $z \notin ii-ker(\{y\})$, we have $\{y\} \cap ii-Cl(\{z\}) = \emptyset$. Since $x \in ii-Cl(\{z\})$, $ii-Cl(\{x\}) \subset ii-Cl(\{z\})$ and $\{y\} \cap ii-Cl(\{x\}) = \emptyset$. Therefore, it follows that $ii-Cl(\{x\}) \neq ii-Cl(\{y\})$. Now $ii-ker(\{x\}) \neq ii-ker(\{y\})$ implies that $ii-Cl(\{x\}) \neq ii-Cl(\{y\})$.

(ii) \Rightarrow (i). Suppose that $\text{ii-Cl}(\{x\}) \neq \text{ii-Cl}(\{y\})$. Then there exists a point z in X such that $z \in \text{ii-Cl}(\{x\})$ and $z \notin \text{ii-Cl}(\{y\})$. Then, there exists an ii-open set containing z and therefore x but not y , namely, $y \notin \text{ii-ker}(\{x\})$ and thus $\text{ii-ker}(\{x\}) \neq \text{ii-ker}(\{y\})$.

Theorem 6.12. Let (X, \mathfrak{T}) be a topological space. Then $\bigcap \{\text{ii-Cl}(\{x\}) : x \in X\} = \phi$ if and only if $\text{ii-ker}(\{x\}) \neq X$ for every $x \in X$.

Proof. Necessity. Suppose that $\bigcap \{\text{ii-Cl}(\{x\}) : x \in X\} = \phi$. Assume that there is a point y in X such that $\text{ii-ker}(\{y\}) = X$. Let x be any point of X . Then $x \in V$ for every ii-open set V containing y and hence $y \in \text{ii-Cl}(\{x\})$ for any $x \in X$. This implies that $y \in \bigcap \{\text{ii-Cl}(\{x\}) : x \in X\}$. But this is a contradiction.

Sufficiency. Assume that $\text{ii-ker}(\{x\}) \neq X$ for every $x \in X$. If there exists a point y in X such that $y \in \bigcap \{\text{ii-Cl}(\{x\}) : x \in X\}$, then every ii-open set containing y must contain every point of X . This implies that the space X is the unique ii-open set containing y . Hence $\text{ii-ker}(\{y\}) = X$ which is a contradiction. Therefore, $\bigcap \{\text{ii-Cl}(\{x\}) : x \in X\} = \phi$.

Theorem 6.13. A topological space (X, \mathfrak{T}) is ii- R_0 if and only if for every x and y in X , $\text{ii-Cl}(\{x\}) \neq \text{ii-Cl}(\{y\})$ implies $\text{ii-Cl}(\{x\}) \cap \text{ii-Cl}(\{y\}) = \phi$.

Proof. Necessity. Suppose that (X, \mathfrak{T}) is ii- R_0 and $x, y \in X$ such that $\text{ii-Cl}(\{x\}) \neq \text{ii-Cl}(\{y\})$. Then, there exists $z \in \text{ii-Cl}(\{x\})$ such that $z \notin \text{ii-Cl}(\{y\})$ (or $z \in \text{ii-Cl}(\{y\})$ such that $z \notin \text{ii-Cl}(\{x\})$). There exists $V \in \text{ii-O}(X)$ such that $y \notin V$ and $z \in V$, hence $x \in V$. Therefore, we have $x \notin \text{ii-Cl}(\{y\})$. Thus $x \in [X - \text{ii-Cl}(\{y\})] \in \text{ii-O}(X)$, which implies $\text{ii-Cl}(\{x\}) \subset [X - \text{ii-Cl}(\{y\})]$ and $\text{ii-Cl}(\{x\}) \cap \text{ii-Cl}(\{y\}) = \phi$.

Sufficiency. Let $V \in \text{ii-O}(X)$ and let $x \in V$. We still show that $\text{ii-Cl}(\{x\}) \subset V$. Let $y \notin V$, that is $y \in X - V$. Then $x \neq y$ and $x \notin \text{ii-Cl}(\{y\})$. This shows that $\text{ii-Cl}(\{x\}) \neq \text{ii-Cl}(\{y\})$. By assumption, $\text{ii-Cl}(\{x\}) \cap \text{ii-Cl}(\{y\}) = \phi$. Hence $y \notin \text{ii-Cl}(\{x\})$ and therefore $\text{ii-Cl}(\{x\}) \subset V$.

Theorem 6.14. A topological space (X, \mathfrak{T}) is ii- R_0 if and only if for any points x and y in X , $\text{ii-ker}(\{x\}) \neq \text{ii-ker}(\{y\})$ implies $\text{ii-ker}(\{x\}) \cap \text{ii-ker}(\{y\}) = \phi$.

Proof. Suppose that (X, \mathfrak{T}) is an ii- R_0 space. Thus by **Theorem 6.11**, for any points x and y in X if $\text{ii-ker}(\{x\}) \neq \text{ii-ker}(\{y\})$ then $\text{ii-Cl}(\{x\}) \neq \text{ii-Cl}(\{y\})$. Now we prove that $\text{ii-ker}(\{x\}) \cap \text{ii-ker}(\{y\}) = \phi$. Assume that $z \in \text{ii-ker}(\{x\}) \cap \text{ii-ker}(\{y\})$. By $z \in \text{ii-ker}(\{x\})$ and **Theorem 6.6**, it follows that $x \in \text{ii-Cl}(\{z\})$. Since $x \in \text{ii-Cl}(\{x\})$, by **Theorem 6.2**, $\text{ii-Cl}(\{x\}) = \text{ii-Cl}(\{z\})$. Similarly, we have $\text{ii-Cl}(\{y\}) = \text{ii-Cl}(\{z\}) = \text{ii-Cl}(\{x\})$. This is a contradiction. Therefore, we have $\text{ii-ker}(\{x\}) \cap \text{ii-ker}(\{y\}) = \phi$.

Conversely, let (X, \mathfrak{T}) be a topological space such that for any points x and y in X , $\text{ii-ker}(\{x\}) \neq \text{ii-ker}(\{y\})$ implies $\text{ii-ker}(\{x\}) \cap \text{ii-ker}(\{y\}) = \phi$. If $\text{ii-Cl}(\{x\}) \neq \text{ii-Cl}(\{y\})$, then by **Theorem 6.11**, $\text{ii-ker}(\{x\}) \neq \text{ii-ker}(\{y\})$. Hence, $\text{ii-ker}(\{x\}) \cap \text{ii-ker}(\{y\}) = \phi$ which implies $\text{ii-Cl}(\{x\}) \cap \text{ii-Cl}(\{y\}) = \phi$. Because $z \in \text{ii-Cl}(\{x\})$ implies that $x \in \text{ii-ker}(\{z\})$ and therefore $\text{ii-ker}(\{x\}) \cap \text{ii-ker}(\{z\}) \neq \phi$. By hypothesis, we have $\text{ii-ker}(\{x\}) = \text{ii-ker}(\{z\})$. Then $z \in \text{ii-Cl}(\{x\}) \cap \text{ii-Cl}(\{y\})$ implies that $\text{ii-ker}(\{x\}) = \text{ii-ker}(\{z\}) = \text{ii-ker}(\{y\})$. This is a contradiction. Therefore, $\text{ii-Cl}(\{x\}) \cap \text{ii-Cl}(\{y\}) = \phi$ and by **Theorem 6.2**, (X, \mathfrak{T}) is an ii- R_0 space.

Theorem 6.15. For a topological space (X, \mathfrak{T}) the following properties are equivalent:

- (i) (X, \mathfrak{T}) is an ii- R_0 space.
- (ii) For any non-empty set A and $G \in \text{ii-O}(X)$ such that $A \cap G \neq \phi$, there exists $F \in \text{ii-C}(X)$ such that $A \cap F \neq \phi$ and $F \subset G$.
- (iii) For any $G \in \text{ii-O}(X)$, we have $G = \bigcup \{F \in \text{ii-C}(X) : F \subset G\}$.
- (iv) For any $F \in \text{ii-C}(X)$, we have $F = \bigcap \{G \in \text{ii-O}(X) : F \subset G\}$.
- (v) For every $x \in X$, $\text{ii-Cl}(\{x\}) \subset \text{ii-ker}(\{x\})$.

Proof. (i) \Rightarrow (ii). Let A be a non-empty subset of X and $G \in \text{ii-O}(X)$ such that $A \cap G \neq \emptyset$. There exists $x \in A \cap G$. Since $x \in G \in \text{ii-O}(X)$, $\text{ii-Cl}(\{x\}) \subset G$. Set $F = \text{ii-Cl}(\{x\})$, then $F \in \text{ii-C}(X)$, $F \subset G$ and $A \cap F \neq \emptyset$.

(ii) \Rightarrow (iii). Let $G \in \text{ii-O}(X)$, then $G \supset \cup \{F \in \text{ii-C}(X) : F \subset G\}$. Let x be any point of G . There exists $F \in \text{ii-C}(X)$ such that $x \in F$ and $F \subset G$. Therefore, we have $x \in F \subset \cup \{F \in \text{ii-C}(X) : F \subset G\}$ and hence $G = \cup \{F \in \text{ii-C}(X) : F \subset G\}$.

(iii) \Rightarrow (iv). Obvious.

(iv) \Rightarrow (v). Let x be any point of X and $y \notin \text{ii-ker}(\{x\})$. There exists $V \in \text{ii-O}(X)$ such that $x \in V$ and $y \notin V$, hence $\text{ii-Cl}(\{y\}) \cap V = \emptyset$. By (iv), $(\cap \{G \in \text{ii-O}(X) : \text{ii-Cl}(\{y\}) \subset G\}) \cap V = \emptyset$ and there exists $G \in \text{ii-O}(X)$ such that $x \notin G$ and $\text{ii-Cl}(\{y\}) \subset G$. Therefore $\text{ii-Cl}(\{x\}) \cap G = \emptyset$ and $y \notin \text{ii-Cl}(\{x\})$. Consequently, we obtain $\text{ii-Cl}(\{x\}) \subset \text{ii-ker}(\{x\})$.

(v) \Rightarrow (i). Let $G \in \text{ii-O}(X)$ and $x \in G$. Let $y \in \text{ii-ker}(\{x\})$, then $x \in \text{ii-Cl}(\{y\})$ and $y \in G$. This implies that $\text{ii-ker}(\{x\}) \subset G$. Therefore, we obtain $x \in \text{ii-Cl}(\{x\}) \subset \text{ii-ker}(\{x\}) \subset G$. This shows that (X, \mathfrak{T}) is an ii-R_0 space.

Corollary 6.16. For a topological space (X, \mathfrak{T}) the following properties are equivalent:

(i) (X, τ) is an ii-R_0 space.

(ii) $\text{ii-Cl}(\{x\}) = \text{ii-ker}(\{x\})$ for all $x \in X$.

Proof. (i) \Rightarrow (ii). Suppose that (X, \mathfrak{T}) is an ii-R_0 space. By **Theorem 6.15**, $\text{ii-Cl}(\{x\}) \subset \text{ii-ker}(\{x\})$ for each $x \in X$. Let $y \in \text{ii-ker}(\{x\})$, then $x \in \text{ii-Cl}(\{y\})$ and by **Theorem 6.2**, $\text{ii-Cl}(\{x\}) = \text{ii-Cl}(\{y\})$. Therefore, $y \in \text{ii-Cl}(\{x\})$ and hence $\text{ii-ker}(\{x\}) \subset \text{ii-Cl}(\{x\})$. This shows that $\text{ii-Cl}(\{x\}) = \text{ii-ker}(\{x\})$.

(ii) \Rightarrow (i). Follows from **Theorem 6.15**.

Theorem 6.17. For a topological space (X, \mathfrak{T}) the following properties are equivalent:

(i) (X, \mathfrak{T}) is an ii-R_0 space.

(ii) If F is ii-closed , then $F = \text{ii-ker}(F)$.

(iii) If F is ii-closed and $x \in F$, then $\text{ii-ker}(\{x\}) \subset F$.

(iv) If $x \in X$, then $\text{ii-ker}(\{x\}) \subset \text{ii-Cl}(\{x\})$.

Proof. (i) \Rightarrow (ii). Let F be an ii-closed and $x \notin F$. Thus $(X - F)$ is an ii-open set containing x . Since (X, \mathfrak{T}) is ii-R_0 , $\text{ii-Cl}(\{x\}) \subset (X - F)$. Thus $\text{ii-Cl}(\{x\}) \cap F = \emptyset$ and by **Theorem 6.7**, $x \notin \text{ii-ker}(F)$. Therefore $\text{ii-ker}(F) = F$.

(ii) \Rightarrow (iii). In general, $A \subset B$ implies $\text{ii-ker}(A) \subset \text{ii-ker}(B)$. Therefore, it follows from (ii), that $\text{ii-ker}(\{x\}) \subset \text{ii-ker}(F) = F$.

(iii) \Rightarrow (iv). Since $x \in \text{ii-Cl}(\{x\})$ and $\text{ii-Cl}(\{x\})$ is ii-closed , by (iii), $\text{ii-ker}(\{x\}) \subset \text{ii-Cl}(\{x\})$.

(iv) \Rightarrow (i). We show the implication by using **Theorem 6.4**. Let $x \in \text{ii-Cl}(\{y\})$. Then by **Theorem 6.6**, $y \in \text{ii-ker}(\{x\})$. Since $x \in \text{ii-Cl}(\{x\})$ and $\text{ii-Cl}(\{x\})$ is ii-closed , by (iv), we obtain $y \in \text{ii-ker}(\{x\}) \subset \text{ii-Cl}(\{x\})$. Therefore $x \in \text{ii-Cl}(\{y\})$ implies $y \in \text{ii-Cl}(\{x\})$. The converse is obvious and (X, \mathfrak{T}) is ii-R_0 .

Definition 6.18. A topological space (X, \mathfrak{T}) is said to be ii-R_1 if for x, y in X with $\text{ii-Cl}(\{x\}) \neq \text{ii-Cl}(\{y\})$, there exist disjoint ii-open sets U and V such that $\text{ii-Cl}(\{x\}) \subset U$ and $\text{ii-Cl}(\{y\}) \subset V$.

Theorem 6.19. A topological space (X, \mathfrak{T}) is ii-R_1 if it is ii-T_2 .

Proof. Let x and y be any points of X such that $\text{ii-Cl}(\{x\}) \neq \text{ii-Cl}(\{y\})$. By **Theorem 5.10**, every ii-T_2 space is ii-T_1 . Therefore, by **Theorem 4.4**, $\text{ii-Cl}(\{x\}) = \{x\}$, $\text{ii-Cl}(\{y\}) = \{y\}$ and hence $\{x\} \neq \{y\}$. Since (X, \mathfrak{T}) is ii-T_2 , there exist disjoint ii-open sets U and V such that $\text{ii-Cl}(\{x\}) = \{x\} \subset U$ and $\text{ii-Cl}(\{y\}) = \{y\} \subset V$. This shows that (X, \mathfrak{T}) is ii-R_1 .

Theorem 6.20. If a topological space (X, \mathfrak{T}) is ii-symmetric, then the following are equivalent:

- (i) (X, \mathfrak{T}) is ii- T_2 .
- (ii) (X, \mathfrak{T}) is ii- R_1 and ii- T_1 .
- (iii) (X, \mathfrak{T}) is ii- R_1 and ii- T_0 .

Proof. Straightforward.

Theorem 6.21. For a topological space (X, \mathfrak{T}) the following statements are equivalent:

- (i) (X, \mathfrak{T}) is ii- R_1 .
- (ii) If $x, y \in X$ such that $\text{ii-Cl}(\{x\}) \neq \text{ii-Cl}(\{y\})$, then there exist ii-closed sets F_1 and F_2 such that $x \in F_1, y \notin F_1, y \in F_2, x \notin F_2$ and $X = F_1 \cup F_2$.

Proof. Obvious.

Theorem 6.22. If (X, \mathfrak{T}) is ii- R_1 , then (X, \mathfrak{T}) is ii- R_0 .

Proof. Let U be an ii-open set such that $x \in U$. If $y \notin U$, since $x \notin \text{ii-Cl}(\{y\})$, we have $\text{ii-Cl}(\{x\}) \neq \text{ii-Cl}(\{y\})$. So, there exists an ii-open set V such that $\text{ii-Cl}(\{y\}) \subset V$ and $x \notin V$, which implies $y \notin \text{ii-Cl}(\{x\})$. Hence $\text{ii-Cl}(\{x\}) \subset U$. Therefore, (X, \mathfrak{T}) is ii- R_0 .

Corollary 6.23. A topological space (X, \mathfrak{T}) is ii- R_1 if and only if for $x, y \in X, \text{ii-ker}(\{x\}) \neq \text{ii-ker}(\{y\})$, there exist disjoint ii-open sets U and V such that $\text{ii-Cl}(\{x\}) \subset U$ and $\text{ii-Cl}(\{y\}) \subset V$.

Proof. Follows from **Theorem 6.11**.

Theorem 6.24. A topological space (X, \mathfrak{T}) is ii- R_1 if and only if $x \in X - \text{ii-Cl}(\{y\})$ implies that x and y have disjoint ii-open neighbourhoods.

Proof. Necessity. Let $x \in X - \text{ii-Cl}(\{y\})$. Then $\text{ii-Cl}(\{x\}) \neq \text{ii-Cl}(\{y\})$, so, x and y have disjoint ii-open neighbourhoods.

Sufficiency. First, we show that (X, \mathfrak{T}) is ii- R_0 . Let U be an ii-open set and $x \in U$. Suppose that $y \notin U$. Then, $\text{ii-Cl}(\{y\}) \cap U = \emptyset$ and $x \notin \text{ii-Cl}(\{y\})$. There exist ii-open sets U_x and U_y such that $x \in U_x, y \in U_y$ and $U_x \cap U_y = \emptyset$. Hence, $\text{ii-Cl}(\{x\}) \subset \text{ii-Cl}(U_x)$ and $\text{ii-Cl}(\{x\}) \cap U_y \subset \text{ii-Cl}(U_x) \cap U_y = \emptyset$. Therefore, $y \notin \text{ii-Cl}(\{x\})$. Consequently, $\text{ii-Cl}(\{x\}) \subset U$ and (X, \mathfrak{T}) is ii- R_0 . Next, we show that (X, \mathfrak{T}) is ii- R_1 . Suppose that $\text{ii-Cl}(\{x\}) \neq \text{ii-Cl}(\{y\})$. Then, we can assume that there exists $z \in \text{ii-Cl}(\{x\})$ such that $z \notin \text{ii-Cl}(\{y\})$. There exist ii-open sets V_z and V_y such that $z \in V_z, y \in V_y$ and $V_z \cap V_y = \emptyset$. Since $z \in \text{ii-Cl}(\{x\}), x \in V_z$. Since (X, \mathfrak{T}) is ii- R_0 , we obtain $\text{ii-Cl}(\{x\}) \subset V_z, \text{ii-Cl}(\{y\}) \subset V_y$ and $V_z \cap V_y = \emptyset$. This shows that (X, \mathfrak{T}) is ii- R_1 .

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